

APPROACHES TO THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR IN THE COUNTRY

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Abstract

Relevance: Sustainable development of the agricultural sector is one of the key tasks of the modern world in the context of global climate change, environmental degradation and growing demand for food. This is especially important for countries where the agricultural sector plays a significant role in the economy and social development. In the context of accelerated growth in the demand for environmentally friendly products and increasing requirements for food quality and safety, sustainable agricultural development is becoming increasingly important.

Research objectives: The purpose of this study is to analyze various approaches to the sustainable development of the agricultural sector, to consider the problems and challenges faced by the agricultural sector in the process of transition to sustainable farming models, and proposals for optimizing these models taking into account local conditions and characteristics.

Novelty: The novelty of this study lies in an integrated approach to the analysis of the sustainable development of the agricultural sector with an emphasis on the adaptation of activities to local conditions and regional peculiarities. The article examines both theoretical aspects and practical examples of successful implementation of sustainable agricultural models in various countries, including the use of environmentally friendly technologies and innovative methods of natural resource management.

Conclusions: The study shows that in order to achieve sustainable development of the agricultural sector, it is necessary to introduce a systematic approach that includes the effective use of land, water and biological resources, minimizing negative environmental impacts, as well as the use of modern biotechnologies and information systems. It is also important to take into account social aspects and ensure the participation of the local population in management and decision-making processes. By 2030, sustainable agricultural development should bring significant economic, social and environmental benefits.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the sustainable development of the agricultural sector requires an integrated and systematic approach, including the coordination of pilot projects, the use of innovative technologies and management methods, as well as the active participation of all stakeholders. The implementation of such approaches will ensure reliable food supply, improve the quality of life of the population and preserve natural resources for future generations.

Keywords: national economy, agricultural sector, sustainable development, supply chain, government regulation, improvement.

Introduction

Sustainable agriculture has attracted widespread attention from countries around the world as a new trend and a new model for the development of agriculture in the future. Due to the historical past, differences in national conditions and understanding of the development of sustainable agriculture, problems inevitably arise in the implementation of sustainable agriculture strategies in different countries and regions. There are different models and approaches. For example, sustainable agriculture in China as a whole contributes to the creation of a way to develop effective ecological agriculture [Altieri, 2002]. Therefore, the choice of specific models and approaches is diverse, but the principle of adapting activities to local conditions and highlighting regional features should be a priority. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development requires new agricultural production methods that ensure adequate, safe and environmentally friendly nutrition while respecting human rights [United Nations, 2015]. FAO member countries share a common vision of sustainable food and agriculture, and eco-agriculture is a key strategy guiding us in advancing the sustainable transformation of food systems [FAO, 2021]. By optimizing the use of local

and renewable resources and knowledge, ecological agricultural systems enable agricultural production systems to ensure productivity by fully exploiting ecosystem benefits such as pest control, pollination, soil health and soil erosion prevention [Altieri, 2002]. The conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity leads to reliable ecosystem services and sustainable agriculture. Ecological agriculture uses as few potentially harmful agricultural chemicals as possible, reducing the negative impact of agriculture on human health and the environment [Pretty et al., 2005]. Ecological agriculture promotes the re-localization of food and helps to promote sustainable and healthy nutrition.

The main part

Sustainable agriculture is agriculture that steadily meets the needs of modern humans in the quantity and quality of agricultural products without prejudice to the interests of future generations, through the management, protection and sustainable use of natural resources, regulation of agricultural systems and technologies [Altieri, 2002]. "Agriculture", which effectively uses land, water, animal and plant resources, does not cause environmental degradation, is technically feasible, economically efficient and is widely recognized by

society [FAO, 2021]. At a time when the country's agriculture is making great strides, a number of problems caused by overexploitation of agricultural resources, overuse of agricultural products, overexploitation of groundwater, overload of agriculture by internal and external pollution are becoming more pronounced, and sustainable agricultural development is fraught with great problems. Environmental pollution issues are coming to the fore, and the task of ensuring the quality and safety of agricultural products is becoming even more difficult [11]. Endogenous pollution in agriculture is serious. The rate of use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides is less than one—third, the rate of processing of agricultural film is less than two—thirds, the effective cleaning of cattle and poultry manure is less than twice, the phenomenon of burning straw is serious. The removal of rural garbage and sewage is strictly insufficient. The increase in environmental pollution in agriculture and rural areas directly affects the quality and safety of agricultural products [Pretty et al., 2005]. When an ecosystem degrades, agricultural development faces many challenges. Measures aimed at expanding the "green" economy to achieve sustainable development against the background of environmental pollution, reduction of natural resources and growing demand are of great importance in the world [Abbasov, 2007]. It is no coincidence that in "Azerbaijan 2030: national priorities for socio-economic development", approved by President Ilham Aliyev, the 5th priority is called "a country of clean environment and green growth" [2]. The document sets specific tasks related to giving significant importance to the use of environmentally friendly technologies, promoting waste recycling and restoration of polluted territories, and expanding the use of environmentally friendly "green" technologies. The processing process established in Azerbaijan serves to develop a "green economy", expand the production of competitive industrial products, and improve the environmental situation [Gasimli, 2022]. We must pursue policies appropriate to local conditions, implement them in different regions, properly manage the relationship between agricultural production, environmental management and environmental restoration, properly and orderly restore agricultural resources, accelerate the management of environmental problems in agriculture [5]. Sustainable strengthening of environmental protection and agricultural construction, promotion of sustainable use of resources and development of agriculture will lead to positive changes. The integrated production capacity and disaster prevention and mitigation capabilities must be improved to match their resource intensity and environmental potential. First of all, it is necessary to adhere to the coordination of pilot projects — demonstrations and agitation. It is advisable to fully understand the complex and systemic nature of sustainable agricultural development, a general account of various types of resource resources and the environmental environment in different regions, and pilot work on unresolved problems. It is important to strive to solve the technical problems that limit sustainable agricultural development and promote the mechanism of action of sustainable agricultural development, explore and generalize

successful models that can be reproduced and promoted, gradually expand the scope of demonstration and stimulation in accordance with local conditions and create a favorable system for sustainable agricultural development [12]. By 2030, sustainable agricultural development will achieve the necessary results, which will bring obvious economic, social and environmental benefits [8]. Currently, positive changes have been achieved in the transformation of agricultural development methods, the integrated production potential of agriculture is constantly being improved, the structure of agriculture is being optimized, and the level of quality and safety of agricultural products is constantly increasing. The level of protection and efficiency of the use of agricultural resources have been significantly improved, the environmental problems of agriculture, forests, meadows, lakes, wetlands and other ecosystem functions have been gradually solved, which have been effectively restored and strengthened, and the rate of biodiversity reduction has gradually decreased [Food Journal, 2017]. Conclusions By 2030, the sustainable development of agriculture will yield remarkable results [6]. A new model of sustainable agricultural development has been created with a strong guarantee of supply, efficient use of resources, a good production environment, a stable ecosystem, rich farmers and beautiful pastoral landscapes [Azərbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin, 2021]. The reintegration of territories liberated from occupation as a result of the victory into the general economy of the country will create new opportunities in this area. The promotion of sustainable agricultural development currently and in the future faces unprecedented historical opportunities [6]. First, there is an increasing consensus on sustainable agriculture. The concepts of green development, circular development and low-carbon development are deeply rooted in the hearts of people and have formed a social consensus on sustainable development [9]. Secondly, the material base for sustainable agricultural development is increasingly being strengthened. The comprehensive national and financial strength of our country continues to grow, the policy of strengthening agriculture, benefiting farmers, enriching farmers continues to grow, the production of basic agricultural products such as grain increases from year to year [Abbasov, 2007]. Thirdly, scientific and technical support for sustainable agricultural development is becoming increasingly reliable. The essence of traditional agricultural technology has been widely inherited, modern biotechnologies, information technologies, new materials and modern equipment are changing every day and are widely used [IPCC, 2021]. Technical models such as ecological agriculture and circular agriculture are constantly being integrated and updated, providing reliable technical support [FAO, 2021]. Fourth, the institutional support for sustainable agricultural development is getting better and better. The reform of agriculture and the reform of the ecological civilization system with constant progress, the constant improvement of the legal and regulatory system and the constant improvement of management capabilities will give vitality and ensure the sustainable development of agriculture [Azərbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin, 2021]. Green

consumption means "choosing environmentally friendly goods and services" to reduce the negative impact of consumption on the environment [Pretty et al., 2005]. The demand for environmentally friendly consumption is also one of the necessary factors to stimulate the sustainable development of enterprises [Altieri, 2002]. Green consumption is not the use of greenery, not the purchase of natural products to protect the environment, but the purchase of environmentally friendly products to protect the Earth; in other words, it is about considering whether our consumer behavior is less harmful or even beneficial to the environment [FAO, 2021]. If consumers can implement environmentally friendly actions and ideas in their lives and choose products with environmentally friendly labels, and the government and consumers can work together, enterprises can be encouraged to produce and sell more environmentally friendly products [IPCC, 2021]. Green enterprises and environmentally friendly enterprises are part of one of the fastest growing industries in the world [United Nations, 2015]. This gives creative entrepreneurs a great opportunity not only to find financial success and opportunities, but also to engage in business that has a positive impact on the world [Pretty et al., 2005]. Green enterprises can take many forms. In fact, green enterprises want to prioritize sustainable development through various business practices or the introduction of certain technologies [Altieri, 2002]. For example, a farm that uses less water than a traditional farm to produce the same crop can be considered a green business [Pretty et al., 2005]. Another example is a company that installs solar panels in homes to reduce dependence on fossil fuels [IPCC, 2021]. These are just a few examples, but the possibilities are almost limitless, as many traditional enterprises can turn into green businesses [FAO, 2021]. Sustainability is a key aspect of green business [Altieri, 2002]. This means that enterprises can operate and scale with minimal negative impact on the environment or people [Pretty et al., 2005]. This may also include fair labor practices in traditionally unfair areas or in industries that often obtain raw materials using environmentally friendly methods [United Nations, 2015]. By making the supply of raw materials more sustainable, the company can become an environmentally friendly or environmentally friendly business [FAO, 2021].

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